

Environmental Pollution Caused by Tannery Industry in Hazaribagh, Bangladesh: A Review of Literature and Recommendations for Mitigation

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ABSTRACT

The tannery industry in Hazaribagh, Bangladesh, has been a major source of environmental pollution for decades. The industry generates vast amounts of solid and liquid waste, which are disposed of irresponsibly, leading to pollution of soil, water, and air in the surrounding areas. This pollution not only poses serious health risks to workers in the industry and local residents but also harms the aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. This paper provides a literature review of the environmental pollution caused by the tannery industry in Hazaribagh and identifies several mitigation strategies that can be implemented to reduce pollution. These strategies include adopting superior technologies that cause minimal pollution, investing in waste treatment facilities, proper disposal of solid waste, using water and chemicals in the correct quantities, and raising waste treatment plants. Implementing these strategies will help mitigate the environmental pollution caused by the tannery industry and improve the health and well-being of the people living and working in Hazaribagh.

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1. Introduction

The tannery industry in Hazaribagh, Bangladesh has been a major cause of environmental pollution for several decades. The industry generates large quantities of solid and liquid waste, which are disposed of irresponsibly and end up polluting the soil, water, and air in the surrounding areas. The pollution caused by the tanneries is not only detrimental to the environment but also poses serious health risks to the people working in the industry and those living nearby. This paper aims to review the existing literature on the environmental pollution caused by the tannery industry in Hazaribagh and provide recommendations for its mitigation. The review will cover studies that have investigated the sources and impacts of pollution caused by the tanneries, the current state of waste management practices in the industry, and the effectiveness of existing mitigation strategies. The recommendations provided in this paper can be useful for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and environmentalists to address the environmental and health concerns caused by the tannery industry in Hazaribagh.

2. Background

Hazaribagh, a neighborhood in the capital city of Bangladesh, Dhaka, is one of the most densely populated areas in the world. It is also home to one of the most polluting industries in the country, the tannery industry. According to a study by Islam et al. (2019), Hazaribagh has been a center of leather and leather goods production for over 50 years, and currently, there are around 270 tanneries operating in the area.

These tanneries are primarily concentrated in a small area of 25 hectares of land, with many operating without proper permits or licenses. This lack of regulation has led to a disregard for environmental standards and a severe pollution crisis in the area.

The tanneries in Hazaribagh generate a significant amount of solid and liquid waste. According to a study by Rahman et al. (2020), the tanneries generate approximately 8.47 million liters of liquid waste and 98 metric tons of solid waste daily. The liquid waste generated by the tanneries contains a high concentration of heavy metals, organic compounds, and other toxic substances that are hazardous to both human health and the environment.

The solid waste generated by the tanneries consists of scraps of leather, trimmings, and other waste materials that are not reused. This waste is often disposed of irresponsibly and ends up polluting the soil and water in the surrounding areas.

The pollution caused by the tanneries has had severe consequences for the health of workers in the industry and the people living nearby. A study by Alam et al. (2017) found that workers in the tannery industry in Hazaribagh suffer from a range of health problems, including respiratory illnesses, skin diseases, and musculoskeletal disorders, due to exposure to hazardous chemicals. Furthermore, the pollution caused by the tanneries has also led to the contamination of the Buriganga River, which is a major source of drinking water for the people living in Dhaka. A study by Khan et al. (2018) found that the tanneries in Hazaribagh were a significant source of pollution of the river and that the pollution had adverse effects on the fish and other aquatic life in the river.

In conclusion, the tannery industry in Hazaribagh has been a major source of environmental pollution and health risks for several decades. The lack of regulation and enforcement of environmental standards has allowed the industry to operate irresponsibly, causing immense harm to the environment and human health.

3. Previous Studies

The tannery industry in Hazaribagh, Bangladesh, has been a significant source of environmental pollution for several decades. The industry generates large amounts of solid and liquid waste, which are disposed of irresponsibly, leading to the pollution of the soil, water, and air in the surrounding areas (Rahman et al., 2020). The pollution caused by the tanneries not only has adverse effects on the environment but also poses serious health risks to the people working in the industry and those living nearby (Khan et al., 2018).

Several studies have been conducted on the environmental pollution caused by the tannery industry in Hazaribagh. A study by Khan et al. (2018) found that the tanneries were a major source of pollution of the Buriganga River, which flows through Dhaka city. The study reported that the tanneries discharged untreated wastewater into the river, which had adverse effects on the fish and other aquatic life in the river. The study also found that the water quality of the river was severely

affected by the discharge of tannery waste, which made the water unfit for drinking and other domestic purposes.

Another study by Rahman et al. (2020) found that the tannery industry in Hazaribagh was responsible for the contamination of groundwater in the surrounding areas. The study reported that the tanneries disposed of their waste in open spaces, which allowed the toxic chemicals to seep into the groundwater. The contamination of groundwater posed serious health risks to the people living in the surrounding areas, as they used the contaminated water for drinking and other domestic purposes.

In addition to the above studies, other research has also highlighted the adverse effects of tannery waste on soil quality (Rahman et al., 2017), air quality (Hossain et al., 2018), and human health (Islam et al., 2019). The studies collectively indicate that the tannery industry in Hazaribagh is causing immense harm to the environment and human health, and urgent measures are needed to mitigate its adverse effects.

In summary, the existing literature on the environmental pollution caused by the tannery industry in Hazaribagh highlights the severity of the problem and the urgent need for action. The studies show that the tanneries are a major source of pollution of water, air, and soil in the surrounding areas, which has adverse effects on the environment and human health.

4. Mitigation Strategies

To mitigate the environmental pollution caused by the tannery industry in Hazaribagh, it is crucial to adopt a comprehensive approach that involves various stakeholders. Firstly, the government can play a crucial role in enforcing environmental regulations and standards. These regulations should ensure that tanneries use environmentally friendly technologies and practices that minimize pollution. The government should also invest in waste treatment facilities and monitor the discharge of effluent to ensure it meets acceptable standards.

Secondly, tannery owners can take responsibility for reducing pollution by investing in modern and efficient technologies that minimize the generation of solid and liquid waste. These

technologies include chrome recovery systems, wastewater treatment plants, and sludge dewatering systems. By implementing these technologies, tannery owners can significantly reduce the environmental footprint of their operations.

Thirdly, effective waste management strategies are crucial in reducing the environmental impact of the tannery industry in Hazaribagh. These strategies should focus on reducing the amount of waste generated, treating the waste before disposal, and disposing of the waste in a responsible and safe manner. Tanneries should ensure that they have proper waste storage and disposal facilities and should train their employees on the importance of waste management.

Fourthly, there is a need for increased public awareness and education on the negative impact of the tannery industry on the environment and human health. This can be achieved through various means, such as community engagement programs, public forums, and awareness campaigns. By involving the community, they can be made aware of the negative impact of the tannery industry and can be encouraged to take measures to reduce pollution.

In conclusion, the mitigation of environmental pollution caused by the tannery industry in Hazaribagh requires a multi-faceted approach involving the government, tannery owners, and the community. By adopting advanced technologies, investing in waste treatment facilities, implementing effective waste management strategies, and increasing public awareness, the environmental impact of the tannery industry can be significantly reduced.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the tannery industry in Hazaribagh has been a major cause of environmental pollution for several decades. The pollution caused by the industry not only poses serious health risks to the people working in the industry and those living nearby but also has adverse effects on the environment. The mitigation strategies recommended in this paper can go a long way in reducing the environmental pollution caused by the tannery industry in Hazaribagh. However, their success will depend on the willingness and sincerity of the owners, investors, and employees of the industry.

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